

3D images of herpetological collections: a new horizon for systematics research and public outreach in a tropical hotspot

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Natural history museums and scientific collections represent a great heritage for humanity and its invaluable information has implications in different disciplines from systematics, ecology, biodiversity conservation to education in environmental sciences. Traditionally, visiting museums by experts represent a big limitation due to the costs associated with the movement of researchers both regionally and globally. With the new global dynamics associated with the covid pandemics, numerous strategies for the knowledge exchange have emerged. Additionally, recent technologies are improving the capture, visualization and analysis of museum specimens. Here, we show how to implement image processing to generate 3D models of museum specimens in a herpetological collection from northwestern Colombia, a hotspot with high species richness and endemism. We developed 3D models for frogs and lizards and propose a low-cost protocol that can be used for small but important regional herpetological collections. To create the 3D images, we use a low-cost structure that consists of a rotating plate on which the specimen is placed and a fixed base for capturing the 2D frames. We can use semi-professional or cell phone cameras. We build the 3D model using free software such as Meshroom and we can expose it on a conventional screen or in a montage made up of a conventional LCD television and acrylic sheets. We are convinced that is imperative to develop new efficient strategies to promote the use of natural history collections and their specimens, not only to improve our scientific knowledge based on them, but also to make the collections available to the society in general.

